

A Unified Data Staging Area for Integrated Analytics

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Abstract

Managing data source heterogeneity remains a persistent challenge in modern analytics environments, where users must integrate datasets spanning diverse databases, file formats, and repositories. This paper presents the Data Staging Area, a core component of DAVE (Data Analytics and Visualization Environment), designed to abstract data source heterogeneity and provide a unified interface for data access within an ELT pipeline. The architecture employs a hybrid storage strategy: file-based datasets are physically staged using MinIO, while database sources are lazily resolved at runtime via stored connection parameters, reducing storage overhead while ensuring data currency. All sources are uniformly described through a MongoDB-backed metadata layer, enabling seamless dataset discovery and pipeline construction. Deployment within real-world analytical workflows demonstrates benefits including separation of concerns, uniform access across heterogeneous sources, user-level data isolation, and improved enterprise interoperability.

Keywords

Data staging area, ETL, ELT, Big Data, Data Integration

1. Introduction

In an increasingly data-centric world, the volume of data being generated continues to grow at an unprecedented rate. Global data creation is projected to reach 221 zettabytes in 2026, representing a significant increase over previous years, driven by the rapid expansion of digital services, IoT devices, and data-intensive industries [1]. This raw data holds immense potential to extract valuable information and provide insights that can improve efficiency, reduce waste, support decision-making processes, and reveal entirely new knowledge.

Data analytics addresses this opportunity by applying techniques that perform data integration operations alongside data mining tasks to derive meaningful insights from raw data. Two primary approaches exist for data integration: Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL), and Extract, Load, and Transform (ELT), and choice between these approaches depends on factors such as data volume, processing infrastructure, and the need for flexible, context-specific transformations. One of the major challenges in data integration lies in the extraction phase, as data sources vary significantly in their connection parameters, data types, and structural formats. This heterogeneity complicates the process of consistently accessing and integrating data from diverse sources, particularly in environments where users need to work with multiple databases, file formats, and data repositories simultaneously.

DAVE (Data Analytics and Visualization Environment) is a framework designed to enable the creation of analytical pipelines in a simple, yet dynamic manner [2] [3]. DAVE adopts the ELT

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approach, incorporating a Data Staging Area as a dedicated component that extracts data from heterogeneous sources and loads it in its raw form into a unified staging environment. The Data Staging Area provides a centralized interface for data access, abstracting away the technical complexities of different data sources. Users can then apply transformations dynamically during pipeline definition and execution, enabling flexible, context-specific data processing without requiring predefined transformation logic during the extraction phase. This approach allows users to seamlessly incorporate datasets into their analytical workflows regardless of origin or format, with transformation logic defined based on specific analytical needs rather than predetermined during data ingestion.

This paper focuses specifically on DAVE's Data Staging Area, describing its design rationale, architectural approach, and implementation. The contribution of this work lies in presenting a practical solution to data source heterogeneity that supports the dynamic construction of analytical pipelines while maintaining simplicity and accessibility for end users. The paper addresses why this component was necessary within DAVE's architecture, how it was implemented to meet these requirements, and identifies directions for future enhancement.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides background on existing approaches to data integration and staging, reviewing ETL and ELT paradigms and identifying open challenges in data source heterogeneity and interoperability. Section 3 describes the design rationale, technology choices, and implementation of the Data Staging Area. Section 4 presents findings from the application of this solution, discussing observed benefits and current limitations. Finally, Section 5 outlines directions for future work to extend the capabilities of the Data Staging Area.

2. Relation to existing theories and work

Data integration is a key factor in data analytics, as the process of connecting and making data available is paramount for any analytical task. Factors such as data availability, data heterogeneity, and data source heterogeneity influence the design of data analytics systems, particularly regarding data integration approaches.

2.1. Data Integration Approaches

ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) has been the traditional approach since the 1970s [4], consisting of three sequential steps: extracting data from sources, transforming it through preprocessing and harmonization, and loading the cleaned data into a warehouse. While ETL has evolved from manual code-intensive processes to GUI-based tools leveraging ML and AI, it suffers from scalability challenges as transformation bottlenecks increase with data volume [5]. The transformation step, occurring before loading, requires significant computational resources and time, particularly when dealing with large volumes of data. This creates a rigid pipeline where transformation logic must be predefined before data becomes available for analysis.

The alternative ELT (Extract, Load, Transform) approach, enabled by cloud computing advances, loads raw data directly into the warehouse before transformation [6]. This fundamental difference allows data analytics systems to perform transformations on demand and execute tasks directly over raw data. ELT provides several advantages: it leverages horizontal scaling with big data technologies like Hadoop [7] and Spark [8], enables multiple transformation pipelines over the same raw data without re-extraction, and allows transformation logic to be defined based on specific analytical needs rather than predetermined during data ingestion. The separation between data acquisition and transformation makes ELT more suitable for modern cloud-based analytics platforms where storage is abundant, and transformation can be performed using distributed computing resources [9].

2.2. Data Staging Patterns

Data staging areas serve as intermediate storage between data sources and target systems during ETL or ELT processes [5]. In ETL scenarios, staging areas temporarily hold extracted data before transformation and loading. In ELT scenarios, staging areas serve as the primary repository for raw

data, enabling multiple downstream transformations without repeated extraction from source systems. Staging areas enable consolidation from multiple sources, facilitate format standardization, and optimize performance by offloading processing tasks. Modern staging architectures embrace containerization technologies and implement metadata tracking to map data flow from sources through transformations to consumption points, providing transparency and facilitating data lineage tracking.

2.3. Open Challenges in Data Integration and Interoperability

Despite advances in ETL/ELT and staging architectures, the literature consistently reports several unresolved challenges in data integration and interoperability.

Organizations face complex challenges integrating heterogeneous data sources, including syntactic heterogeneity (data types and formats), semantic heterogeneity (meaning and interpretation), and terminological heterogeneity (naming conventions) such as highlighted by Putrama et al. in [10]. These challenges manifest at schema, instance, and semantic levels, compounded by data redundancy, incompleteness, and application-specific designs. Connection parameters and authentication mechanisms vary widely across database systems, cloud platforms, and file repositories, requiring specialized technical knowledge that limits accessibility for domain experts with analytical expertise but limited infrastructure knowledge. Traditional integration approaches often require extensive configuration and specialized expertise, creating barriers to rapid analytical workflow development.

3. Research Approach and Implementation

The Data Staging Area was designed around three fundamental requirements: ensuring workflows always access the most current version of datasets; maintaining consistent data source availability to prevent disruption of scheduled executions; and abstracting data source heterogeneity to provide uniform access regardless of whether data originates from files or databases.

3.1. Design Principles

The Data Staging Area employs a hybrid approach balancing storage efficiency with data accessibility. Rather than physically storing all data like a traditional warehouse, the architecture differentiates between file-based and database sources based on their characteristics and usage patterns. File-based sources, which typically contain smaller datasets, are stored in full. Database sources, which provide larger datasets connected to production systems, are accessed via stored connection parameters while data remains at the source. This strategy reduces DAVE's storage requirements while maintaining the ELT paradigm's benefit of providing raw data for on-demand transformation.

This distinction reflects fundamental differences in data source characteristics. Database sources typically contain large, frequently updated datasets serving production systems. Physically copying such data would create synchronization challenges, increase storage costs, and introduce staleness. By storing only connection parameters and retrieving data at workflow runtime, the staging area ensures analytical workflows operate on current data without separate synchronization processes. While this lazy loading approach creates runtime dependency on external systems, it guarantees data currency, reduces storage overhead, and aligns with typical usage patterns where databases maintain high availability as authoritative sources.

Files represent discrete datasets that change less frequently than operational databases, making physical storage practical. Storing files within DAVE ensures workflow reliability even if original sources become unavailable, enables complete control over data access, and simplifies permission management for scheduled executions.

All staged sources are accompanied by metadata in a NoSQL database, including information about data structure, source type, connection details, and ownership. This uniform metadata representation provides users with a consistent interface when selecting datasets, abstracting technical

differences between file and database sources while maintaining the information necessary for workflow execution.

3.2. Technology Selection

MongoDB [11] was selected as the metadata repository due to its flexible schema-less design, which accommodates varying metadata structures for different data source types without requiring predefined schemas. This flexibility is essential in a system where users may register diverse data sources with different characteristics. MongoDB's document-oriented model aligns naturally with the JSON-based metadata representations used throughout DAVE's architecture [2], simplifying integration with the backend API and frontend components. Additionally, MongoDB provides efficient querying capabilities for retrieving available datasets and their associated metadata during workflow construction.

MinIO [12] serves as the object storage solution for file-based datasets. As an S3-compatible object storage system, MinIO provides a standardized interface for storing and retrieving files in various formats including CSV, Parquet, and JSON. MinIO's lightweight deployment model aligns with DAVE's goal of providing a standalone framework that can be deployed across different environments without extensive infrastructure requirements. The system's scalability supports growing data volumes while maintaining consistent performance, and its compatibility with big data processing frameworks like Apache Spark enables seamless integration with DAVE's transformation operators.

3.3. Implementation Methodology and Results

The Data Staging Area implementation consists of three primary components: a user interface for dataset registration, a metadata management layer for tracking staged datasets, and a runtime data access layer integrated with workflow execution. Dataset registration occurs through a dedicated interface where users either upload files or provide database connection parameters. Upon submission, the system validates the provided information, stores files in MinIO if applicable, extracts and stores metadata in MongoDB, and makes the dataset available in the workflow construction interface. This user interface for dataset registration can be seen in Figure 1.

During workflow construction, which can be seen in Figure 2, users select datasets from a unified dropdown list populated from the metadata repository. The Dataset Connector operator, when added to a workflow, presents this list without distinguishing between file and database sources, maintaining the abstraction principle. At workflow execution time, the operator retrieves the appropriate metadata from MongoDB and either loads the file from MinIO or establishes a connection to the specified database, performing the actual data extraction only when the workflow task executes. This runtime resolution ensures that database workflows access current data while file-based workflows load the staged version, all through the same operator interface.

At runtime, each connector independently resolves its source: files are loaded from MinIO and database sources are queried using stored connection parameters. In both cases, the retrieved data is materialized into a common in-memory format, either a Pandas or Spark dataframe, passed through MongoDB between operators. This runtime harmonization ensures that downstream operators receive data in a consistent, interoperable format regardless of the original source type, enabling transformation, joining, and aggregation across heterogeneous datasets within the same pipeline.

Figure 1: Data Staging Environment for datasets management

Figure 2: Selection of dataset during workflow creation

4. Findings

The implementation and deployment of the Data Staging Area within DAVE have revealed several benefits and limitations that inform both its current utility and future development directions.

Benefits

- **Separation of Concerns.** The Data Staging Area decouples data preparation from workflow execution, enabling users to register datasets once and reuse them across multiple workflows. The staging phase focuses on making data available, while transformation logic resides within pipeline operators, aligning with the ELT paradigm.
- **Uniform Access Interface.** The abstraction layer masks data source heterogeneity. Users interact with a single Dataset Connector operator and dropdown list, regardless of whether datasets originate from files or databases, eliminating the need to understand technical differences between source types.
- **User Isolation and Data Privacy.** Dataset isolation at the user level ensures each user accesses only their own registered datasets through metadata tracking in MongoDB, preventing accidental access and simplifying permission management.
- **Simplified Pipeline Creation.** By abstracting data source complexity, users no longer specify connection parameters, file paths, or authentication details. Dataset selection becomes a simple dropdown choice, particularly valuable in DAVE's visual programming environment.
- **Interoperability.** The Data Staging Area serves as a bridging layer enabling diverse data sources to participate in analytical workflows through a common interface. Workflows remain independent of specific data infrastructure (PostgreSQL [13], MySQL [14], CSV, Parquet), facilitating system evolution. The metadata layer provides a foundation for data discovery, lineage tracking, and impact analysis.

Limitations

- **Absence of Data Validation at Ingestion.** The Data Staging Area operates without preprocessing capabilities. Data is stored in raw form without validation or profiling, meaning data quality issues are discovered during workflow execution rather than at registration time.
- **No Dataset Versioning.** Updates overwrite previous versions without maintaining historical records, affecting reproducibility when underlying datasets change.
- **Single-User Access Model.** Datasets cannot be shared between users, restricting collaboration and requiring team members to independently register the same datasets, leading to duplication and potential inconsistencies.
- **Runtime Dependency on External Systems.** Runtime dependency on external systems means the lazy loading approach for databases introduces potential points of failure in enterprise environments with strict service level agreements. In the current implementation, connection timeouts or failures cause the pipeline to fail and retry on the next scheduled run, with more robust error handling planned for future iterations.

5. Future Directions

The identified limitations motivate several enhancements. Dataset versioning would enable workflow reproducibility and allow users to compare different data versions. Extending the access model to support dataset sharing would address collaboration constraints, allowing teams to work from common, centrally registered data sources.

Introducing lightweight data profiling and quality checks during registration would provide earlier feedback on data suitability, reducing the risk of discovering issues only at workflow execution. Visual dataset exploration features such as structure preview, sample rows, and basic statistics would improve the staging area user experience.

The rich metadata captured during ingestion presents opportunities for enhanced interactivity. Making metadata available to downstream operators could enable context-aware workflow construction, such as automatically suggesting compatible transformation operators based on selected dataset structure. Addressing runtime dependency on external databases through fallback mechanisms or selective caching would improve reliability in production and enterprise deployment scenarios.

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